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APPLICATION OF VIRTUAL REALITY TECHNOLOGY IN MOBILE WORK MACHINE ENGINEERING EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The connection between a high motivation to study and a positive learning outcomes is generally known. In engineering education, authentic learning environments have been found to be one of the most important factors to increase students' motivation to study. However, working with a real artefact is not always possible.

A promising method for the creation of authentic learning environments is the use of virtual reality (VR). One VR environment has been developed to study the structures of forest machine crane and harvester head. The purpose of this article is to describe the practicality of this VR environment in engineering education. We focus on the following research question: How do students experience the VR learning environment?

The ongoing research project will be conducted with mechanical engineering students throughout three academic years. Thus far, the obtained results indicate that the students experience increased meaningfulness when learning in a VR environment. However, integrating VR technology into courses is not an easy task. At this point of research, the learning outcomes has not yet been measured. The results of the study will contribute to the development of the VR environment and further research by comparing the learning outcomes of the real and VR environments in a more detailed research framework.

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1 INTRODUCTION

A new generation of engineering students equipped with good information technology skills is embarking on university studies. They have high expectations that their institutions will use modern methods to teach them working-life skills, which they will need in their future work environments. During studies, we often hear students complaining that their education is not modern enough, not practical enough and not interesting enough. We also hear professors complaining that students have little motivation to learn. These challenges require universities to develop their teaching and embrace the use of new technologies.

The implementation of new teaching and learning technologies does not happen overnight. In connection with the introduction of new technologies, teachers' design skills are challenged. However, although they present more possibilities, advanced teaching technologies also present many challenges, and integrating information and communications technology (ICT) into classroom practices continues to be a challenging task for many teachers [1]. To address these challenges, technological pedagogical and content knowledge (TPACK) is a relatively recently developed theoretical framework designed to guide research in teachers' use of ICT [2]. The question also easily arises as to whether the additional work required for the introduction of technology is worth the effort. Factors influencing student motivation to learn can be outlined using many theories [3]. In the context of this study, perspectives of the self-determination theory [4] have been utilized.

VR has been in use in certain skill learning applications for some time. For instance, flight simulators and also driving simulators are in wide use. Currently, VR has been applied also in engineering education, training and research [5]. Technology enables an authentic experience and combines students' abilities to use modern information technology with the needs of teachers to create motivating learning environments [6]. The hypothesis of this study is that VR learning environments are also well suited for a mobile work machine engineering education.

One particular VR environment has been developed to study the structures of forest machine crane and harvester head. The purpose of this article is to describe the practicality of this VR environment in mobile work machine engineering education. We focus on the following research question: How do students experience the VR learning environment as part of their engineering education?

The following is structured as follows: Section 2 discusses the research method used, focusing on the research strategy and data sources. Section 3 introduces the results of the research. Section 4 discusses the findings of the study. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with future directions and final remarks.

2 METHODOLOGY

One key area of research related to teaching and learning that has recently gained attention is the study of technology-based interventions to increase learning motivation. Research can be carried out by many different methods. The research described in this article is the first in a series of interventions aimed at improving the learning process through a VR learning environment. The research will be conducted using the educational design research (EDR) method. The strength of this method can be demonstrated by the ability to carry out carefully planned scientific research while simultaneously producing solutions to problems arising in practical teaching tasks [7]. EDR is well suited for research like this because it is characterized by an iterative structure. In EDR, new knowledge and interventions evolve over time through several stages of research, development and testing [8]. This paper describes the first cycle of research. EDR also allows the combination of different forms of data collection.

2.1 Description of the learning task

The suitability of the VR environment for engineering education was studied in connection with normal teaching in the academic year of 2019-2020. The learning task was included in connection with laboratory courses in automotive and work machine technology. In laboratory courses, students were divided into groups of a few students who do one learning task per teaching session. The duration of the teaching session was three lessons. Thus, the students worked continuously for about 2.5 hours.

Sixteen groups completed the learning task during the school year. Six groups were in their fourth year of engineering studies, eight groups were in their second year, and four groups were exchange students from different countries with different levels of studies. All the students of classes participated in the research. A total of 69 students completed the learning task. Most often, the group size was four students, but configurations of three and five students were also used. With this number of participants, a sufficient amount of data was accumulated to form a reliable overall picture.

The aim of the learning task was to learn the structure and operation of a forest machine crane and a harvester head by dismantling both structures part by part in VR environment. After completing the assignment, the student should be able to name the main components of the assemblies and explain their functions and operating principles. The learning task began under the guidance of a teacher, where the configuration of the VR equipment was reviewed. Next, the equipment was commissioned, i.e. the necessary connections and calibrations were made. After these steps, the user interface and functionalities of the program were further reviewed under the guidance of a teacher. After this, the teacher left the room and the students were began using the VR environment on their own. If problems or a

need for guidance arose during the work, students were instructed to report to the teacher working in the adjacent space.

Because only one VR hardware was available, one student at a time was able to use the virtual environment. The group decided on the length of an individual student's VR period and changed the user of the equipment at appropriate intervals. Other members of the group were able to follow the events in the VR environment through an image projected on the screen. At the same time, they wrote down answers to technical questions, took care of wires and other hazards to the user and guided the student using the equipment based on the screen image.

2.2 Data collection

In connection with the assignment, the group was given a form that included questions about the structure of the crane and harvester head. Students were required to fill out this form together during the assignment. In addition, each student received a personal feedback form related to the VR environment to complete after the learning task. They were also told about the group interview that would take place in connection with the return of the forms. The interview was conducted in a semi-structured format, leaving students with the opportunity to share their experiences also freely.

The purpose of the personal feedback form was to obtain information on how each student experienced the use of the VR environment as part of their engineering education. Students rated the excitement, meaningfulness, immersion in the task and quality of learning. In addition, they evaluated the functionality of the technical implementation in its various areas. The aim was also to find out how they experienced the environment physically, i.e. whether the work caused nausea or other unpleasant feelings. Students were asked to state on a 5-point Likert scale to what extent they agreed or disagreed with the statements. There was also additional questions, which were open in nature, allowing students to express their opinions freely.

In the group discussion at the end of the work, the teacher was given the opportunity to evaluate the students' learning by asking more specific technical questions. The discussion was conducted on the basis of pre-prepared questions that were repeated in each discussion. During the conversation, the teacher got a good overall picture of the students' attitudes toward a new type of learning assignment. The forms and the group discussions thus resulted in both quantitative and qualitative data for analysis.

2.3 Data analysis

To get accurate results from the research questions, the collected data was carefully analyzed. The forms were reviewed by the research team. The numerical evaluations provided by the students were recorded in Excel software to enable

statistical analysis. The answers to the open-ended questions were analyzed together in group discussions. During the discussions, answers were categorized and key findings were recorded. The notes collected during the group interviews with students were also analyzed and the main findings were recorded. Teachers' experiences of using the VR environment as part of their teaching were mirrored in the TPAC framework. Student responses were analyzed in an effort to identify motivational factors in the context of the self-determination theory. The physical effects caused by the VR environment were compared with the results of previous studies.

3 RESULTS

The aim of the study was to obtain information about the usability of the VR learning environment from the perspective of the student. At the beginning of the feedback form, students were asked to compare VR study with traditional classroom instruction on a scale of 1-5. On the scale, a grade of '1' indicated that the student felt that classroom instruction was far superior, while a grade of '5' indicated that the student felt that VR learning was a better option. With a grade of '3', the environments were perceived to be on an equal footing. The following are statistical results supplemented by the answers from open-ended questions. The stage of studies (second or fourth year of engineering student) did not cause significant differences in results.

In general, students felt that the VR environment was a more inspiring environment than the classroom (Q1 average score: 4.6). Immersion in studying was also at a good level (Q2 average score: 4.0), but more students reported that the environment attracts extra gimmicks, which reduced the focus on studying. The meaningfulness of the learning task was perceived as high (Q3 average score: 4.5). The quality of learning was considered somewhat better than the classroom (Q4 average score: 3.7). Although the environment itself did not require the presence of a teacher to function properly, several students did perceive the absence of the teacher as a problem. This was primarily due to questions raised during the work, for which the students were unable to receive answers immediately. Figure 1 shows a comparison with traditional classroom instruction, including standard deviation.

Figure 1. VR learning environment comparison with traditional classroom instruction.

1= classroom is superior, 3=equal footing, 5=VR is superior.

Issues related to the technical implementation of the environment were also assessed numerically on a scale of 1-5. A rating of '1' meant poor technical implementation, while a rating of '5' meant excellent. The classroom as a space was considered to be functional for the use of equipment (Q5 average score: 3.9), although some students wanted more space, allowing for greater possibilities to move during the work. At the same time, the cable for VR glasses was found to restrict movement and even pose a danger if operated alone.

The usability of the VR environment was considered good (Q6 average score: 4.1), indicating that the factors affecting the smooth operation (e.g. the menus, the logic of the functions, etc.) were at a good level. The functionality of the program, on the other hand, received a slightly lower rating than the usability (Q7 average score: 3.7.) This was mainly due to the limited performance of the computer's video card and the resulting momentary image jitter. The veracity of the environment was assessed as good (Q8 average score: 3.8). Figure 2 shows the evaluation of the technical implementation, including standard deviation.

Figure 2. Evaluation of the VR environment technical implementation. 1=poor, 5= excellent

Students rated the physical suitability of the environment for them on a scale of 1-5. A rating of '1' meant that they were only able to use the equipment for a short time due to physical problems. A rating of '5' meant that they felt completely normal throughout the work. In general, students felt that the use of the VR environment was physically suitable for them (Q9 average score: 4.3, standard deviation: 0,32). Many students reported mild physical problems while using the equipment. The most common symptom was sweating, which was mentioned by five students. Other physical symptoms reported included nausea, headache, dizziness, eye fatigue and a feeling of pressure on the face caused by device glasses. In total, 43% of students report some of these feelings. However, the symptoms were generally felt to be mild and did not prevent anyone from using the equipment.

Disadvantages were also found. Some students felt that their group caused a feeling of urgency, which made it impossible to study at their own pace. For some, watching the events from the sidelines caused frustration. There was also room for improvement in the application. Now the program only allows disassembly, not the re-installation of parts. This was considered a shortcoming. Another perceived shortcoming was the lack of gamification. At the end of the exercise, for example, the students needed the opportunity to test their skills and thereby receive feedback. This could have been accomplished through gamification; a competition between groups (which was hoped for) which would have motivated even more effective study.

When asked whether VR teaching should be increased, 92,8% of students answered yes, 5,8% were unsure of their opinion and only one student (representing 1,4%) answered in the negative way. The positive answers were justified in various ways, e.g. an increased motivation to study because the method is inspiring and different. A few students appreciated learning the basics using traditional methods and

suggested that the VR method would be most effective when supplementary and should not be used as a substitute for other teaching methods. Problems related to nausea and other physical symptoms also emerged when considering the increased use of VR environments. The possibility of making one's own video recordings during VR studies also emerged as a developmental proposal, in which case the contents could be returned later if necessary.

4 DISCUSSION

Question of motivation is familiar to every student. Motivation to learn stems from many factors. The self-determination theory suggests that people have a need to do things independently and they want to do things that they find enjoyable [9]. The results of this study support the effect of this premise on study motivation. The VR environment allows events to be managed at your own pace. An appreciation of this was reflected in the high ratings of the meaningfulness of the learning task.

Another premise of self-determination theory is the human need for relatedness [9]. This type of exercise can be done as groupwork. This can be seen as a strength because then students can discuss the project and reflect on technical issues together. The feeling of competence is also one of the factors that increases motivation [9]. Students hope that in the VR environment they could test their own skills and get feedback instantaneously. The highest motivation to learn is achieved when the three factors described above occur simultaneously [3]. By designing a VR environment to support these three areas that promote motivation, it is possible to achieve good learning outcomes.

The teacher's ability to design courses has a direct impact on how successful the learning process will be. As the teacher makes a decision on the use of new teaching technology, he or she also increases the number of factors to consider when designing a course. This results in a complex design challenge. Traditional content and pedagogical knowledge are still needed, but they are accompanied by a need for technological knowledge. With new emerging technologies, there is a danger that the role of technology will be overemphasized in teaching [10]. In connection with this research, this fact became apparent, e.g. in terms of how time is allocated. Although the students' IT skills were good, a relatively large proportion of the time spent on the learning task was used in the orientation of the technology.

The idea that the use of VR technology would reduce the teacher's role as a learning facilitator is flawed [6]. The teacher must continue to lead the learning and ensure that the learning materializes. Although the VR environment frees from acquiring and learning to use physical teaching models, the successful integration of VR equipment into teaching requires a significant amount of planning and expertise. The 'teacher as a researcher' approach also promotes and lowers the threshold for the use of new teaching methods and equipment.

The validity of the study can be assessed from many different perspectives. The participation of the entire classes prevented bias in the sample. All students who participated in the research also returned the study forms. One factor in favor of good validity is the relatively low standard deviation of the results. However, research always has its limitations. In this case, predictive validity can be questioned. Although students found the VR environment motivating, there is not yet clear evidence that it has positive effect to learning outcomes.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Alongside teachers' pedagogical and content skills, there is a strong need for technological skills. However, technology is always just a tool. When defining the competence objectives of a course, the teacher should at the same time think about the big picture, in which the assessment of competence also plays an important role, as well as in teaching and learning tasks. At its best, VR technology offers opportunities to enrich teaching and learning situations. If the available VR environment contributes to the learning objectives of the course, its use in the light of this study is well justified.

The research described in this article will continue in the next EDR cycles. The next goal is to implement an even more precise research design and to collect data on the discrepancies in the levels of learning between the virtual and real learning environment. This is possible by implementing a learning environment with the same content virtually and with a real forest machine. The aim of further research is to find out whether it is possible to detect clear differences in the results of learning between a real and a virtual environment.

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